

A Study of Problems of Security Guards in Kolhapur District

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Abstract:- There are many security agencies in Kolhapur District. The objective of the study was to find out the problems of security guard in Kolhapur district. Thematic, comparative and content analysis methods were used to analyses open-ended questions. The study found out that working conditions have a significant positive impact on them, there is a significant difference problem between fixed contracts and open-ended contract and that there are various significance problems between male and female employees. The study concluded that security guards have many problems. It also concluded that the nature of contract and working affects job satisfaction. The study recommended that agency of security consider improving their working conditions to increase security guard satisfaction.

Keywords:- Security Guards, Problems, Recommendations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The private security industry has flourished globally over the past two decades, especially in developing countries such as India where many people in low-density areas and those who own companies feel unsafe and are willing to pay for private policing. The remarkable growth of security industries can be attributed to the prevailing socio-economic environment where many people are coming up with new business ventures that provide a ready market for their services. It can also be ascribed to the ongoing harsh economic conditions, which have led to high unemployment rates and a consequent rise in crime. The economic conditions have led to a rise of exploited workers. Exploited Workers can be referred to as underpaid, overworked, long hours at work and the worker is still unable to provide basic needs e.g. food, housing and other survival items. It is also appropriate to mention that where business markets are under the control of capitalists, they exploit the workers more than anything one can think of. Due to the ever-increasing unemployment rate, people are queuing up to be exploited just to keep themselves alive. It's no question that our industry deals with daily physical security threats in our facilities, airports, hospitals, schools, and retail stores. The only way to effectively conduct business is for physical security teams to proactively manage risk. Without it, organizations would be unable to host employees, guests, students, patients, or visitors, ship goods, track assets, travel, and more.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Ritchie et al (2007), the private security industry in Africa has grown tremendously in recent years. The resulting unemployment and increased economic insecurity fuelled an increase in crime. Private companies stepped into the void and created thousands of security jobs. Unfortunately, these jobs are characterized by poor working conditions, low wages and rampant casualization. These jobs are important to workers who value them as a crucial source of income. A security guard should work four days a week with three consecutive days as rest days. This is not the case in most security companies as companies are short staffed. The predominant form of employment, particularly in newly established firms, is the fixed-term contract or 'contract work'. There is also the open contract, which is commonly referred to as a 'permanent contract' and is prevalent in well-established security firms. One can remain a contract worker for as long as the contract is renewed.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study was guided by the Two-Factor Theory also known as Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory. Herzberg's findings revealed that certain characteristics of a job are consistently related to job satisfaction, while different factors are associated with job Dissatisfaction.

➤ *Statement of The Problem:*

The economic conditions in India have led to a rise in the exploitation of workers especially the semi semi-skilled security guards. The exploitation of these workers has been manifested by underpayment, lack of health and safety provision, lack of social protection, overworking (long hours) at work and the employer's unable to provide adequate basic needs to cater for the workers welfare e.g. food, housing and other survival items. There have been unfair labour practices especially in 2015 when employers willy-nilly retrenched workers (security guards) as a result of an infamous Supreme Court ruling which allowed employers to terminate one's employment without need to justify by giving 3 months' notice based on *precedence of common law*. A lot of workers including guards fell victim to this ruling and majority have not been paid even to date their retrenchment packages. Given this background, the researchers were to find out the level of job satisfaction of security guards in light of numerous labour disputes and such exploitation.

➤ *Research Objectives*

- To find out the history of security guard agencies in Kolhapur District.
- To find out the problems of security guards.
- To recommend the problems of security guards.

➤ *Research Questions*

What are the factors that affect the problems of security guards?

- To establish the security guard agencies.
- To recommend means that can reduce the problems of security guards.

IV. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Approach*

A mixed methodology was used encompassing both the phenomenological and positivist philosophies.

➤ *Research Design*

A cross-sectional survey was conducted to collect data from private security guards in the target population, sample and sampling techniques. A sample of 60 private security guards was selected using convenience sampling.

➤ *Study Area*

The study area of the present research is Kolhapur district.

➤ *Instrumentation*

A semi-structured questionnaire was designed to collect information on gender, age, nature of the contract, length of employment, level of education, salary, environment scheduling, working hours, transport arrangements and employee relations. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions with pre-coded responses to allow for easy quantitative analysis and open-ended questions for participants to air their minds Data collection procedure. Permission to conduct the study was sought from the respective security agencies in Kolhapur District. Questionnaires were administered to security guards at their workstations

V. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions with pre-coded responses to allow for easy quantitative analysis and open-ended questions for participants to air their minds Multiple regression analysis and Mann-Whitney U were used in the analysis of data. Multiple regressions were used to determine factors that affect job satisfaction. Part of the analysis of data was based on non-parametric statistical tests since data was measured on non-parametrical. Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference of,

- Problems between fixed contracts and open-ended contracts and
- Problems between male and female employees.

For qualitative data (responses from open-ended questions) findings were analysed using the content analysis method, involving categorization of data, classification, summarization, and coding.

➤ *Problems of Security Guards:*

The Security Benchmark Report is an annual report published by Security magazine. The report details the top issues/Concerns for Security Leaders, which include:

- Workplace Violence
- Covid-19 (and pandemics)
- Business continuity and business resilience
- Cybersecurity
- Civil unrest, disturbances, riots, activists, targeted protests
- Crisis management
- Staffing and training
- Insider threats
- Risk and threat intelligence
- Natural disasters

The researcher has highlighted ten issues of the security guard. The top 5 issues facing security Guards right now are as per the following.

- Workplace Violence
- Hiring and Training
- Cyber and Physical Security
- Outdated Technology
- Covid-19

➤ *Workplace Violence:*

Workplace violence continues to be an issue in healthcare, education, recreation, and more, costing businesses every year. Often, security guards play the role of the first responder as they manage verbal abuse, physical threats and assaults, active shooter threats even homicide with workplace violence prevailing in common areas and facilities, security guards must continue to mitigate physical security vulnerabilities against unwanted visitors, violence, and threatening incidents.

➤ *Hiring and Training:*

Security guard companies are not a one-size-fits-all business. Performance expectations vary from one organization to the next. The skills needed by security guards at a reception area, for example, are very different from the skills needed by those who are working in a large warehouse environment or a remote electrical substation.

Staffing and training require a security plan to use new technologies such as video analytics, mobile devices, and drone robotics. In addition, as the security officer is the first responder and a key player in any organization's security readiness, modern training tactics need to include the ability to make quick and informed decisions and not wait for someone to tell him or her to act in a minor situation.

➤ *Cyber and Physical Security Concerns:*

Security guards may not think that they play a role in a company's cybersecurity strategy, but they should. The most common initial attack vector, compromised credentials, was responsible for 20% of breaches at an average breach cost.

Cybercriminals will use every tool they can to breach a facility and steal data, but criminals are less likely to target a facility that has full-time security teams in place. To mitigate the physical security risks of a data breach, guards can and should play an important role in ensuring that only authorized credentials are allowed into a facility.

➤ *Outdated Technology:*

Modern security teams need modern equipment. The days of sending a guard on tour with only a good torch, strong pair of boots and a walkie-talkie are passed. Security guards need to be outfitted with the latest in guard tracking software to communicate with dispatch, record incidents and stay on top of their assignments. Sending a guard on tour not properly equipped is an added threat to the safety of the security officer in the field and the assets they are responsible for protecting.

VI. COVID-19

In a typical year, guarding companies are focused on threats like visitor management, active shooters, terrorism, and more, and those concerns remain this year. However, the Covid-19 pandemic forced security guards to adapt to new challenges. Stay-at-home mandates meant that fewer employees were going into office buildings and facilities. However, more buildings and facilities are now open, and employers are asking employees to return to work. One challenge is requiring security guards to learn about PPE protocols and employee screening procedures and technologies. It has also tasked guards with handling temperature checks and enforcing mask-wearing, all while trying to protect themselves from the virus. It has called on security guards to handle customer interactions differently, to protect both parties. Even more, the pandemic has created a new perimeter, as many facilities are setting up screenings and checking vaccination status further away from a facility's entrance. These challenges will continue in 2022 and beyond.

Overall, a risk mitigation strategy may not be as difficult to set up as one may think. When security teams are provided with the resources to meet the everyday challenges of their roles; including the proper training, the right tools, and effective leadership, security teams can tip the scales of risk in favour of stability.

VII. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Working overtime is only by agreement unless there is an emergency and the employee has no reasonable excuse for refusing to work. However, the trend seems to be that security guards are actually forced to work overtime, regardless. In the majority of cases, such overtime goes unpaid. This is one of the major grievances raised by

security workers. The payment of overtime is equivalent to 1.5 times the normal hourly rate on a working day of the week, or double the time for a day when the employee concerned would normally be off, private security workers indicated that such payments have been hard to come by. A Workplace Violence. Cybersecurity, Crisis management, Staffing and training, Insider threats, Risk and threat intelligence and Natural disasters are all these problems found in security guards.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION:

The study concluded that security guards have many problems. It also concluded that the nature of the contract affects job satisfaction. More specifically it concluded that employees with fixed-term contracts lack job satisfaction more than those with open ended contract. The study also concluded that working conditions including payment of overtime and resting time have a significant impact on job satisfaction. It is recommended that where possible employees should offer open-ended contracts so that the level of job satisfaction within employees will be improved. It is also recommended that security guards must be given enough time to rest and in cases where they work overtime, they should be paid theirs over time.

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